

Generalized Synchronization of Different Chaotic Systems via Linear Mapping

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Joydev Ghosh

Research Scholar
Department Of
Mathematics
Bankura University
Bankura, West Bengal,
India

Mohammad Ali Khan

Assistant Professor
Department Of
Mathematics
Ramananda College
Bishnupur, West Bengal,
India

Abstract	One of the most striking discoveries in the study of chaos is that chaotic systems can be made synchronized with each other. Synchronization of chaos is a phenomenon that may occur when two or more chaotic dynamical systems are coupled. There are different type of generalized synchronization method have studied earlier. But here we propose different schemes for generalized synchronization of different chaotic and hyperchaotic systems with mismatch parameters. Numerical simulation results are presented to show the efficiency of our proposed schemes.
Keywords	Generalized Synchronization, Mismatch Parameter, Lorenz System, Lorenz-Stenflo system, Rossler System
Introduction	In view of the potential applications of chaotic synchronization, many different chaotic synchronization methods have been developed recently. Among them are: Identical synchronization (synchronization in the usual sense) [1] impulsive synchronization [2] and generalized synchronization [3]. The so-called generalized synchronization can give much richer dynamics than identical ones. Applications of GS may be wider or more practical than those of identical synchronization because there always exist parameter mismatches and distortions in the physical world. Since the pioneer work by Pecora and Carroll [1], control and synchronization of chaotic systems has received great attention due to their potential real world applications in engineering, physics, chemistry, control theory and secure communications. Up to now, many chaotic systems have been developed and studied by the researchers.
Objective of study	In this paper, we present a novel different schemes for generalized synchronization of different chaotic and hyperchaotic systems with mismatch parameters. Numerical simulation results are presented to show the efficiency of our proposed schemes.
Review of Literature	Lu chaotic system [4], Chen chaotic system [5], Lorenz chaotic system [6], Genesio chaotic system [7], Liu chaotic system [8], supply chain chaotic system [9], economic and finance chaotic systems [10] are some of them. Among these chaotic systems, the economics and finance chaotic systems, which were discovered in 1985, have great impact on prominent economics at present. Since the economic crisis, the role of chaos has great attention, which shows the existence of butterfly effect and chaos in the finance system. During the past two decades, many control and synchronization methods have been introduced to synchronize (hyper)chaotic systems. Active method [11], adaptive method [12], projective method [13], phase synchronization [14], backstepping method [15], sliding mode method [16], state feedback control [17] and linear feedback controller [18] are some of the investigated methods. The majority of the aforementioned synchronization methods provide a non linear feedback controller to control the behavior of chaotic systems. Undoubtedly, the linear feedback controller is easier to be implemented than other nonlinear methods. Linear feedback control has been successfully utilized for the control by many different chaotic systems. Chaotic system has attracted many researchers' attention since its powerful use in various fields, such as secure communication, information processing, biological engineering and chemical processing. Since the seminal work of Ott, Grebogi and Yorke (OGY) [19], there has been an increasing interest in recent years in the study of controlling chaotic systems. Many methods have been proposed to realize chaos control, such as backstepping method [15], adaptive control [12], sliding mode control [16]. These methods can stabilize the chaotic system asymptotically. In practical engineering process, we may want to stabilize the system as quickly as possible. So it is important to study finite-time stabilization of the chaotic system.
Analysis	Gernal Theory of Coupling

We consider the drive system as

$$\dot{x} = f(x), \tag{1}$$

and the response system as follows

$$\dot{y} = g(y) + u, \tag{2}$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$. u is the controller by which we want to derive using Lyapunov stability theory.

In order to study of synchronization we consider error system as $e = O(x) - N(y)$, where $O(x)$ is the observable variable and $N(y)$ is the noticable variable, therefore

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}(t) &= D[O(x)]\dot{x} - D[N(y)]\dot{y}, \\ &= D[O(x)]f(x) - D[N(y)](g(y) + u). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3}$$

where $e \in \mathbb{R}^h$ with $h \leq \max \{m, n\}$. Then the error dynamical system between the drive system (1) and the response system (2) can be written as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}(t) &= DO(x)\dot{x} - DN(y)\dot{y}, \\ &= DO(x)f(x) - DN(y)\{g(y) + u(t)\}, \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{4}$$

where $DO(x)$ and $DN(y)$ are the jacobian matrices of the vector function $O(x)$ and $N(y)$ respectively, i.e.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} DO(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_2} & \cdots & \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_m} \\ \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_2} & \cdots & \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\delta o_h(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_h(x)}{\delta x_2} & \cdots & \frac{\delta o_h(x)}{\delta x_m} \end{bmatrix} \\ DN(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_2} & \cdots & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_n} \\ \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_2} & \cdots & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\delta n_h(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_h(y)}{\delta y_2} & \cdots & \frac{\delta n_h(y)}{\delta y_n} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{5}$$

With the proper choice of the controller $u(t)$, the above error systems can be written as $\dot{e}(t) = Ae(t)$, such that the matrix A is negative definite. Therefore all the eigenvalues of the matrix A have negative real parts. Hence by the theory of finite time stability of dynamical system, the system (1) and (2) are in GFTS for a constant time $T = T(e(0)) > 0$. For the above system (1) and (2) are in GFTS if there exist a constant $T = T(e(0)) > 0$ such that $\lim_{t \rightarrow T} \|e(t)\| = \lim_{t \rightarrow T} \|O(x) - N(y)\| = 0$, and $\|e(t)\| = 0$ if $t > T$, then the synchronization about the drive system (1) and the response system (2) are achieved within a finite time. The main goal of the paper is that, for a choice of feedback control $u(t)$ such that for any given drive system (1) and response system (2) are in GFTS.

Numerical Simulation Results

In order to show the effectiveness of our approach, two numerical simulation results are used to discuss the applicability of proposed method and validity the theoretical results.

Simulation 1

In simulation 1, we choose Lorenz system as drive system and Lorenz-Stenflo system as response system. The Lorenz and Lorenz-Stenflo system can be described by the following ODE.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= \alpha(x_2 - x_1), \\ \dot{x}_2 &= \gamma x_1 - x_1 x_3 - x_2, \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_1 x_2 - \beta x_3, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{y}_1 &= \alpha(y_2 - y_1) + sy_4 + u_1, \\ \dot{y}_2 &= \gamma y_1 - y_1 y_3 - y_2 + u_2, \\ \dot{y}_3 &= y_1 y_2 - \beta y_3 + u_3, \\ \dot{y}_4 &= -y_1 - \alpha y_4 + u_4. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

According to (1), the system (6) can be written as $\dot{x} = f(x)$ where

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } f(x) = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha(x_2 - x_1) \\ \gamma x_1 - x_1 x_3 - x_2 \\ x_1 x_2 - \beta x_3 \end{bmatrix}.$$

And according to (2) the system (7) can be written as $\dot{y} = g(y) + u(t)$ where

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \end{bmatrix}, g(y) = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha(y_2 - y_1) + sy_4 \\ \gamma y_1 - y_1 y_3 - y_2 \\ y_1 y_2 - \beta y_3 \\ -y_1 - \alpha y_4 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } u(t) = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Case I

In this case we assume the observable variable $O(x)$ of the system (1) and noticeable variable $N(y)$ for the system (2) in the following manner

$$\left. \begin{aligned} O(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1 + x_2 \\ x_1 + x_3 \end{bmatrix}, \\ N(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} y_1 + y_2 \\ y_3 + y_4 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Henceforth

$$\left. \begin{aligned} DO(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_2} & \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_3} \\ \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_2} & \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_3} \end{bmatrix}, \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} DN(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_2} & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_3} & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_4} \\ \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_2} & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_3} & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_4} \end{bmatrix}, \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Then the GFTS error of the two chaotic (Lorenz system) and hyperchaotic (Lorenz-Stenflo system) systems are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} e(t) &= O(x) - N(y), \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} o_1(x) - n_1(y) \\ o_2(x) - n_2(y) \end{bmatrix}, \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1 + x_2 - y_1 - y_2 \\ x_1 + x_3 - y_3 - y_4 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

Therefore the error system becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1(t) \\ \dot{e}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha(x_2 - x_1) \\ \gamma x_1 - x_1 x_3 - x_2 \\ x_1 x_2 - \beta x_3 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha(y_2 - y_1) + s y_4 + u_1 \\ \gamma y_1 - y_1 y_3 - y_2 + u_2 \\ y_1 y_2 - \beta y_3 + u_3 \\ -y_1 - \alpha y_4 + u_4 \end{bmatrix},$$

i.e.,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= (\gamma - \alpha)x_1 + (\alpha - 1)x_2 - x_1 x_3 \\ &\quad - (\gamma - \alpha)y_1 - (\alpha - 1)y_2 - s y_4 + y_1 y_3 - u_1 - u_2, \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= \alpha(x_2 - x_1) + x_1 x_2 - \beta x_3 \\ &\quad - y_1 y_2 + \beta y_3 + y_1 + \alpha y_4 - u_3 - u_4. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

With the choice of the feedback controllers

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1 &= (\alpha + \gamma)x_1 + (2\alpha - 1)x_2 + \alpha x_3 - x_1 x_3, \\ u_2 &= -\gamma y_1 + (1 - 2\alpha)y_2 - \alpha y_3 - (\alpha + s)y_4 + y_1 y_3, \\ u_3 &= (\beta - \alpha - 10)x_1 + (\alpha - 10)x_2 - y_1 y_2, \\ u_4 &= 11y_1 + 10y_2 + (\alpha - \beta)y_4 + x_1 x_2, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= -\alpha\{e_1(t) + e_2(t)\}, \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= 10e_1(t) - \beta e_2(t). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

Hence the above error system can be written as $\dot{e}(t) = Ae(t)$ where

$$\dot{e}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1(t) \\ \dot{e}_2(t) \end{bmatrix}, A = \begin{bmatrix} -\alpha & -\alpha \\ 10 & -\beta \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } e(t) = \begin{bmatrix} e_1(t) \\ e_2(t) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Case II

For case II, observable variable $O(x)$ and noticeable variable $N(y)$ can be chosen in following manner

$$\left. \begin{aligned} O(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1 x_2 \\ x_1 + x_2 \\ x_1 - x_3 \end{bmatrix}, \\ N(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} y_1 - y_2 \\ y_2 - y_3 + y_4 \\ y_3 + y_4 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

Therefore

$$DO(x) = \left. \begin{aligned} & \left[\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_2} & \frac{\delta o_1(x)}{\delta x_3} \\ \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_2} & \frac{\delta o_2(x)}{\delta x_3} \\ \frac{\delta o_3(x)}{\delta x_1} & \frac{\delta o_3(x)}{\delta x_2} & \frac{\delta o_3(x)}{\delta x_3} \end{array} \right] , \\ & \left[\begin{array}{ccc} x_2 & x_1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 \end{array} \right] , \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

and

$$DN(y) = \left. \begin{aligned} & \left[\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_2} & \frac{\delta n_1(y)}{\delta y_3} \\ \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_2} & \frac{\delta n_2(y)}{\delta y_3} \\ \frac{\delta n_3(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_3(y)}{\delta y_2} & \frac{\delta n_3(y)}{\delta y_3} \\ \frac{\delta n_4(y)}{\delta y_1} & \frac{\delta n_4(y)}{\delta y_2} & \frac{\delta n_4(y)}{\delta y_3} \end{array} \right] , \\ & \left[\begin{array}{cccc} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{array} \right] . \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (17)$$

Then the GFTS error of the two chaotic (Lorenz system) and hyperchaotic (Lorenz-Stenflo system) systems are connected by

$$e(t) = \left. \begin{aligned} & O(x) - N(y), \\ & \left[\begin{array}{c} o_1(x) - n_1(y) \\ o_2(x) - n_2(y) \\ o_3(x) - n_3(y) \end{array} \right] , \\ & \left[\begin{array}{c} x_1x_2 - y_1 + y_2 \\ x_1 + x_2 - y_2 + y_3 - y_4 \\ x_1 - x_3 - y_3 - y_4 \end{array} \right] . \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

Therefore the error system becomes

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \left[\begin{array}{c} \dot{e}_1(t) \\ \dot{e}_2(t) \\ \dot{e}_3(t) \end{array} \right] &= \left[\begin{array}{ccc} x_2 & x_1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha(x_2 - x_1) \\ \gamma x_1 - x_1x_3 - x_2 \\ x_1x_2 - \beta x_3 \end{array} \right] \\ &- \left[\begin{array}{cccc} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} \alpha(y_2 - y_1) + sy_4 + u_1 \\ \gamma y_1 - y_1y_3 - y_2 + u_2 \\ y_1y_2 - \beta y_3 + u_3 \\ -y_1 - \alpha y_4 + u_4 \end{array} \right] , \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (19)$$

i.e.,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= \alpha x_2(x_2 - x_1) + x_1(\gamma x_1 - x_1x_3 - x_2) \\ &\quad - \alpha(y_2 - y_1) - sy_4 + \gamma y_1 - y_2 - y_1y_3 - u_1 + u_2, \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= \alpha(x_2 - x_1) + \gamma x_1 - x_1x_3 - x_2 \\ &\quad - (\gamma - 1)y_1 + y_2 + y_1y_2 + y_1y_3 - \beta y_3 + \alpha y_4 - u_2 + u_3 - u_4, \\ \dot{e}_3(t) &= \alpha(x_2 - x_1) - x_1x_2 + \beta x_3 \\ &\quad - y_1y_2 + y_1 + \beta y_3 + \alpha y_4 - u_3 - u_4. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (20)$$

Now, we choose the feedback controllers u_1, u_2, u_3 and u_4 in the following manner

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1 &= \alpha x_2^2 + x_1(\gamma x_1 - x_1 x_3 - x_2) + \gamma y_1 - y_2 - s y_4 - y_1 y_3, \\ u_2 &= 0, \\ u_3 &= \frac{1}{2}[x_1 x_3 - (\alpha + 1)x_1 x_2 - 2y_1 y_2 - y_1 y_3 - \gamma x_1 + (\beta - 1)x_3 \\ &\quad + (\alpha + \gamma)y_1 - \alpha y_2 + 2(\beta - 1)y_3 - y_4], \\ u_4 &= \frac{1}{2}[(\alpha - 1)x_1 x_2 - x_1 x_3 + (\gamma + 2 - 2\alpha)x_1 + 2\alpha x_2 + (\beta - 1)x_3 \\ &\quad + (2 - \alpha - \gamma)y_1 + \alpha y_2 + (2\alpha - 1)y_4 + y_1 y_3]. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (21)$$

Therefore the error system (20) becomes

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= -\alpha e_1(t), \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= -\alpha e_1(t) - e_2(t), \\ \dot{e}_3(t) &= -e_3(t). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

The system (22) can be rewritten as $\dot{e}(t) = Ae(t)$ where the coefficient matrix A can be written as $A = \begin{bmatrix} -\alpha & 0 & 0 \\ -\alpha & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$. Since A is negative definite, therefore the system (6) and (7) are in generalized finite time synchronous state.

Simulation 2

In simulation 2, we choose Rössler system as drive system and hyperchaotic Rössler system as response system. The Rössler system and hyperchaotic Rössler system can be described by the following ODE

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= -x_2 - x_3, \\ \dot{x}_2 &= x_1 + ax_2, \\ \dot{x}_3 &= b + x_3(x_1 - c), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (23)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{y}_1 &= -y_2 - y_3 + u_1, \\ \dot{y}_2 &= y_1 + a_1 y_2 + y_4 + u_2, \\ \dot{y}_3 &= b_1 + y_1 y_3 + u_3, \\ \dot{y}_4 &= -c_1 y_3 + d_1 y_4 + u_4. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (24)$$

The system (23) is chaotic for $a = 0.2, b = 0.2$ and $c = 5.7$ and the system (24) is chaotic for $a_1 = 0.25, b_1 = 3, c_1 = 0.5$ and $d_1 = 0.05$. According to (1) and (2), the above systems (23) and (24) can be written as

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}, f(x) = \begin{bmatrix} -x_2 - x_3 \\ x_1 + ax_2 \\ b + x_3(x_1 - c) \end{bmatrix}.$$

and

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \end{bmatrix}, g(y) = \begin{bmatrix} -y_2 - y_3 \\ y_1 + a_1y_2 + y_4 \\ b_1 + y_1y_3 \\ -c_1y_3 + d_1y_4 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } u(t) = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Case I

In case I, we assume the observable variable $O(x)$ of the system (1) and noticeable variable $N(y)$ for the system (2) in the following way.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} O(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 + x_2 \\ x_2 + x_3 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}, \\ N(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_1 + y_2 \\ y_2 + y_3 \\ y_3 + y_4 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (25)$$

Hence

$$\left. \begin{aligned} DO(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ DN(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (26)$$

Therefore GFTS error between chaotic and hyperchaotic Rössler systems can be expressed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= -x_2 - x_3 + y_2 + y_3 - u_1, \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= x_1 + (a - 1)x_2 - x_3 \\ &\quad - y_1 + (1 - a_1)y_2 + y_3 - y_4 - u_1 - u_2, \\ \dot{e}_3(t) &= x_1 + ax_2 + b + x_3(x_1 - c) \\ &\quad - y_1 - a_1y_2 - y_4 - b_1 - y_1y_3 - u_2 - u_3, \\ \dot{e}_4(t) &= b + x_3(x_1 - c) - b_1 \\ &\quad - y_1y_3 + c_1y_3 - d_1y_4 - u_3 - u_4. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (28)$$

With the choice of the feedback controllers

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1 &= -x_2 + y_2, \\ u_2 &= 2x_1 + ax_2 - 2x_3 - 2y_1 + (1 - a_1)y_2 + 2y_3 - y_4, \\ u_3 &= x_1x_3 - y_1y_3 - x_1 + x_2 + (3 - c)x_3 \\ &\quad + y_1 - 2y_2 - 3y_3 + b - b_1, \\ u_4 &= x_1 - x_2 - 2x_3 - y_1 + 2y_2 + (c_1 + 2)y_3 - (d_1 + 1)y_4. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (29)$$

the error system (28) becomes

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= -e_1(t) + e_2(t) - e_3(t), \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= -e_2(t) + e_3(t), \\ \dot{e}_3(t) &= -e_3(t), \\ \dot{e}_4(t) &= -e_4(t). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (30)$$

Here the system (30) can be written as $\dot{e}(t) = Ae(t)$ where the coefficient

matrix $A = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$. Since the eigenvalues of the matrix A

has negative real parts, therefore the system (23) and (24) are in GFTS state.

Case III

In case II, the observable variable $O(x)$ and noticeable variable $N(y)$ are chosen as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} O(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_1 + x_2 \\ x_2 + x_3 \end{bmatrix}, \\ N(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_1 + y_2 \\ y_2 + y_3 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

Hence

$$\left. \begin{aligned} DO(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ DN(y) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (32)$$

Then the GFTS error between the systems (23) and (24) can be expressed as

$$e(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 - y_1 \\ x_1 + x_2 - y_1 - y_2 \\ x_2 + x_3 - y_2 - y_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (33)$$

Therefore the error system becomes

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= -x_2 - x_3 + y_2 + y_3 - u_4, \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= x_1 + (a - 1)x_2 - x_3 \\ &\quad - y_1 - (a_1 - 1)y_2 + y_3 - y_4 - u_1 - u_2, \\ \dot{e}_3(t) &= x_1 + ax_2 + x_3(x_1 - c) \\ &\quad - y_1 - a_1y_2 - y_4 - y_1y_3 + b - b_1 - u_2 - u_3. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (34)$$

With the choice of the controllers

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1 &= -3x_1 + x_3 + 3y_1 + 2y_2 + y_3, \\ u_2 &= 5x_1 + ax_2 - 2x_3 - 5y_1 - (a_1 + 2)y_2 - y_4, \\ u_3 &= x_1x_3 - 4x_1 + cx_2 + 2x_3 \\ &\quad + 4y_1 + (2 - c)y_2 - cy_3 - y_1y_3, \\ u_4 &= 3x_1 - x_3 - 3y_1 + y_3, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (35)$$

then the error systems are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1(t) &= -2e_1(t) - e_2(t), \\ \dot{e}_2(t) &= -e_2(t), \\ \dot{e}_3(t) &= -ce_3(t). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (36)$$

The above equation (36) can be written in the form of $\dot{e}(t) = Ae(t)$ where $A = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -c \end{bmatrix}$. Since the eigenvalues of the matrix A has negative real parts, therefore the system (23) and (24) are in GFTS state.

Result and Discussion

In simulation 1, we choose $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.7$, $\gamma = 26.0$ and $s = 1.5$ for the systems (6) and (7). The initial values of the drive system (6) and response system (7) are chosen as $x_1(0) = 0.002$, $x_2(0) = 0.002$, $x_3(0) = 0.002$, $y_1(0) = 0.001$, $y_2(0) = 0.001$, $y_3(0) = 0.001$ and $y_4(0) = 0.001$ for all simulations. In case I, the finite time generalized synchronization error state trajectories for $e_1(t)$ and $e_2(t)$ are shown in Fig.1 and for case II, the error state trajectories for $e_1(t)$, $e_2(t)$ and $e_3(t)$ are shown in Fig.2. The two figures (Fig.1 and Fig.2) confirms that the error state trajectories converges to the origin infinite time. From Fig.1 and Fig.2 indicates the generalized synchronization is achieved between (6) and (7) under the choice of controller $u(t)$, which is represented by equation (13). In simulation 2, we choose $a = b = 0.2$ and $c = 5.7$ for the system (23) and $a_1 = 0.25$, $b_1 = 3$, $c_1 = 0.5$ and $d_1 = 0.5$ for the system (24). For case I, in the simulation 2, the finite time generalized synchronization error state trajectories for $e_1(t)$, $e_2(t)$, $e_3(t)$ and $e_4(t)$ are shown in Fig.3 and in Fig.4, the generalized finite time synchronization are drawn for $e_1(t)$, $e_2(t)$ and $e_3(t)$ accordingly. Fig.3 and Fig.4 confirms that the error state trajectories converges to the origin in finite time. From these figures it is clear that generalized finite time synchronizations are arises for the system (23) and (24) under the controllers (29) and (35) respectively.

Conclusion

The present paper studied the generalized synchronization between chaotic and hyperchaotic systems of different order using feedback control. To effectiveness of our approach numerical simulations are used to discuss the applicability of the proposed method and validity the theoretical results. In society, we have observed that different type of behaviour are arises between two persons under different forcing frequency and forcing amplitude, in which some go in favour of their love and other go against their love and also the nature of behaviour of two persons are continuously disturbed due to different kind of social disturbances. So the study of generalized synchronization of different order is very important in social sciences. In biological systems, we also observed that the synchronization occur between heart beat and breathing. It is very important to notice that both are

circulatory and respiratory system behave in a synchronous way but their models are in different order. So the study of this paper is very much necessary in biological systems also.

References

1. Pecora, Louis M., and Thomas L. Carroll. "Synchronization in chaotic systems." *Physical review letters* 64.8 (1990): 821.
2. Ao, Wengang, et al. "Finite-time and fixed-time impulsive synchronization of chaotic systems." *Journal of the Franklin Institute* 357.16 (2020): 11545-11557.
3. Lynnyk, Volodymyr, and Sergej Celikovskiy. "Generalized synchronization of chaotic systems in a master-slave configuration." *2021 23rd International Conference on Process Control (PC)*. IEEE, 2021.
4. Singh, Satnesh, Seungyong Han, and S. M. Lee. "Adaptive single input sliding mode control for hybrid-synchronization of uncertain hyper-chaotic Lu systems." *Journal of the Franklin Institute* 358.15 (2021): 7468-7484.
5. Mahmoud, Gamal M., Tassos Bountis, and Emad E. Mahmoud. "Active control and global synchronization of the complex Chen and Lu systems." *International Journal of Bifurcation and Chaos* 17.12 (2007): 4295-4308.
6. Zhang, Fuchen, et al. "Dynamics of a generalized Lorenz-like chaos dynamical systems." *Journal of Applied Analysis and Computation* 11.3 (2021): 1577-1587.
7. Park, Ju H. "Adaptive controller design for modified projective synchronization of Genesio-Tesi chaotic system with uncertain parameters." *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals* 34.4 (2007): 1154-1159.
8. Yang, Cheng-Hsiung. "Chaos hybrid generalized synchronization of liu-chen system by GYC partial region stability theory." *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience* 10.4 (2013): 825-831.
9. Mondal, Sayantani. "A new supply chain model and its synchronization behaviour." *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals* 123 (2019): 140-148.
10. Wang, Yong-Long, et al. "Deep recurrent neural networks with finite-time terminal sliding mode control for a chaotic fractional-order financial system with market confidence." *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals* 146 (2021): 110881.
11. Hao, Zhang, et al. "Generalized synchronization of hyperchaos and chaos using active backstepping design." *Chinese Physics* 14.1 (2005): 86.
12. Li, Chuang, Fuhong Min, and Chunbiao Li. "Multiple coexisting attractors of the serial-parallel memristor-based chaotic system and its adaptive generalized synchronization." *Nonlinear Dynamics* 94.4 (2018): 2785-2806.
13. Yu, Yongguang, and Han-Xiong Li. "Adaptive generalized function projective synchronization of uncertain chaotic systems." *Nonlinear Analysis: Real World Applications* 11.4 (2010): 2456-2464.
14. Yao, Zhao, et al. "Phase synchronization between a light-dependent neuron and a thermosensitive neuron." *Neurocomputing* 423 (2021): 518-534.
15. Wang, Baofang, Makoto Iwasaki, and Jinpeng Yu. "Command filtered adaptive backstepping control for dual-motor servo systems with torque disturbance and uncertainties." *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 69.2 (2021): 1773-1781.
16. Takhi, Hocine, et al. "Passivity based sliding mode control and synchronization of a perturbed uncertain unified chaotic system." *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation* 181 (2021): 150-169.
17. Ali, M. Syed, and M. Hymavathi. "Synchronization of fractional order neutral type fuzzy cellular neural networks with discrete and distributed delays via state feedback control." *Neural Processing Letters* 53.2 (2021): 929-957.
18. Shi, Lin, Chunmei Zhang, and Shouming Zhong. "Synchronization of singular complex networks with time-varying delay via pinning control and linear feedback control." *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals* 145 (2021): 110805.
19. C. Grebogi, E. Ott, and J. A. Yorke. *Chaotic attractors in crisis*. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*,48(22), 1507(1982).

Figure 1: The finite-time generalized synchronization error state trajectories of systems (6) and (7) with controller (13) in Simulation 1.

Figure 2: The finite-time generalized synchronization error state trajectories of systems (6) and (7) with controller (21) in Simulation 1.

Figure 3: The finite-time generalized synchronization error state trajectories of systems (23) and (24) with controller (29) in Simulation 2.

Figure 4: The finite-time generalized synchronization error state trajectories of systems (23) and (24) with controller (35) in Simulation 2.